

PRINCIPALS ADMINISTRATIVE FUNCTIONS AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL IN NSUKKA EDUCATION ZONE OF ENUGU STATE NIGERIA.

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Abstract: This study examined principals' administrative functions and achievements of secondary school in Nsukka education zone of Enugu state Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to: find out the administrative achievements of male and female principals in their administrative roles basing on their management styles and determine the administrative constraints of principals of urban and rural secondary schools. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design and was carried out in Nsukka Education Zone. It made use of questionnaires as the instrument for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyse the research questions while t – test statistics was used to test the two null- hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The researcher discovered that the major findings are that there is gender difference in establishing discipline between male and female principals in favour of male principals; and that school location has no significant influence on administration constraints of principals in Nsukka Education zone. It was concluded that male principals do better in the area of discipline than their female counterparts and that principals of both urban and rural secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone are constrained with finance, structure/facilities and indiscipline, thereby hindering their effective managerial abilities. It was recommended among other things that the Community or the Government should build quarters to house principals and teachers coming from outside the community in which the school is located.

Keywords: Principals, Administrative functions, Achievements, Secondary school.

Introduction

1.1 Background to the Study

There has been a public outcry against the falling standard of education in Nigeria's public secondary schools. The conduct of the school and the quality of their products are seen by some as a reflection of the level of administrative performance of the principals. Given the National Policy on Education, the principal has an important function to play. Among these roles include providing effective managerial skills and styles in the art and science of administering secondary schools, thereby enhancing better job performance among teachers that could enhance students' academic performance (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). How effective principals are in performing these functions according to Fika, Ibi and Aji (2015) has been a matter of concern to many educationists and general public. The principal, however, can be a male or a female as the case may be. It may

interest one to note that the gender of the principal matters a lot for many scholars as it can affect the administrative effectiveness or performance and achievement expected of the principal. The gender of the principal may equally predict the administrative style that will dominate in running the affairs of the school. This could be accounted by the differences in the psychological make-up of both.

Secondary school education stands in-between the primary and tertiary education. It is an educational institution where the second stage of the three schooling periods, known as secondary education and usually compulsory up to a specified age, takes place. It is a preparatory stage for the societal task. Hence, Ngwokabuenu (2015) says that secondary school/education is meant at preparing the learners for valuable living conditions within the society and training for further education. In this line of thought, Okoroma (2016) understands secondary school as a feeder to tertiary level of education which produces the required manpower for development. Nevertheless, these secondary schools can be grouped into two from the point of view of location: Urban Secondary Schools and Rural Secondary Schools. Alokun and Arijesuyo (2013) noted that many scholars in the area of education in the recent past seemed to have shifted studies from the measures of individuals to the measures of the environment. There has been a prevalence of comparative inferiority of rural schools and this has shown an existence of urban-rural differences in students' academic performance.

However, the State Government exercises control partly directly and partly indirectly, over all secondary schools irrespective of the type of management and location, through their power to accord aid and, or recognition. In Nigeria, there have been some objectives that are outlined for the attainment of secondary education. Such objectives as are contained in Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) (2014) include: Provide holders of the Basic Education Certificate and Junior Arabic and Islamic Studies Certificate with opportunity for education of a higher level, irrespective of sex, social status, religious or ethnic background; offer diversified curriculum to cater for differences in talents, opportunities and future roles; provide trained manpower in applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades; develop and promote Nigeria languages, arts and culture in context of world cultural heritage; inspire students with desire for self-improvements and achievements of excellence; foster national unity with an emphasis on the communities that unite us in our diversity; raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feedings of others, respect the dignity of labour, appreciate those values specified under our broad national goals and live as good citizens.

Administration is seen by Udor (2015) as any formal effort geared towards the realization of set goals using human, material and financial resources. Administration is concerned with performance of executive duties, carrying out of administrative policies and controlling day-to-day operations of an organization. Talking about administration makes up for an inclusion of all processes that combine resources to achieve a set goal. The employment of different styles in administering is known as administrative styles. These administrative styles could enhance the level of performance as well as the achievement of principals, whether male or female. Educational administration has been seen as comprehensive effort intended to achieve some specific educational objectives and it deals with education practice. Its purpose is to bring pupils and teachers under such conditions as will more successfully promote the end of education (Kandel, 2012). This is supported by Balfour and Alibasic (2011) who sees the purpose of educational administration as to enable the right pupils to receive the right education from the right teachers, at a cost within the means of the State, which will enable pupils to profit by their learning.

Secondary School Administration has to do with how secondary schools are managed or administered. For an effective secondary school administration to be achieved, there must be effective supervision of instruction which,

for Osakwe (2010), is the art of over-seeing the Teaching-Learning process, therefore making sure that the school is administered, managed and leads in an effective manner to achieve the educational objectives. It also depends on proper organization which is the process of having a structure and assigning people on the posts to perform specific duties. Therefore, administration of secondary schools must seek to produce quality graduates with employability skills and sustainable alacrity through effective and efficient instructional delivery and students' discipline (Udor, 2015).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

It is quite unfortunate that despite the efforts made by the Federal and State Governments in bringing out objectives of secondary education, what one sees now is never anything impressive or something to write-home about. One of the objectives bordered on raising a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, respect the dignity of labour, appreciate those values specified under Nigerian broad national goals and live as good citizens. A look at what is obtainable now both on those presently undergoing secondary education and the recent products of secondary education shows that this has not been met as it borders on discipline. There is a lot of undisciplined acts portrayed by both the staff and the students which has led to reduction in standard of education and expectations on school learners thereafter. Lack of knowledge, inexperience and negligence on the side of principals as regards their roles in administration of their schools have caused a whole lot of indiscipline and poor performance of students and staff equally. Every year, the society experiences cases of cultism, disregard for teachers/elders, vandalization of facilities in the school, examination misconduct and other nonchalant attitudes from students and some teachers and as such, Mudemb (2013) shows that about 13.5% (boys) and 4.5% (girls) of the students leave school on themselves in fear or are expelled because of these cases of indiscipline. How indiscipline will be curbed, pre-service training for would-be principals for proper knowledge of their role as well as living within or near the school premises were not addressed by scholars, hence, they have contributed to the problem of today. This study tends to proffer a solution to this problem. It is against this background that this study seeks to determine roles of principals in secondary school administration in Nsukka Education zone of Enugu State, Nigeria.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the roles principals play in secondary school administration in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study's objectives are to:

1. Find out the administrative achievements of male and female principals in their administrative roles basing on their management styles.
2. Determine the administrative constraints of principals of urban and rural secondary schools.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

- i. What are the administrative achievements of male and female principals in their administrative roles using the different management styles?
- ii. What are the administrative constraints of principals of urban and rural secondary schools?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following null-hypotheses are formulated to guide the study. Each will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores rating of male and female principals on the extent principals establish discipline among students and staff.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean scores rating of principals on administrative constraints of principals in urban and rural secondary schools.

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Principals Administrative Function

The principal's administrative function encompasses various responsibilities that contribute to the effective management and leadership of a school. These functions include planning, organizing, directing, coordinating, and evaluating educational programs and staff to achieve institutional goals. Scholars have extensively defined and examined the role of principals in educational administration, emphasizing their influence on school effectiveness, teacher performance, and student achievement. According to Bush (2021), the principal's administrative function involves strategic decision-making, resource allocation, and leadership to foster a positive school environment. Effective administration ensures that all stakeholders, including teachers, students, and parents, are aligned with the school's vision and objectives. Similarly, Hallinger and Murphy (2020) assert that principals serve as instructional leaders who shape the curriculum, monitor teaching quality, and create a conducive learning atmosphere. Their administrative role extends beyond supervision to include mentoring, professional development, and policy implementation.

Furthermore, Hoy and Miskel (2018) describe the principal's administrative function as a blend of managerial and leadership duties, where the principal is responsible for structuring the school's operational framework while inspiring staff towards excellence. They highlight that successful administration requires principals to balance bureaucratic functions with transformational leadership practices. In contrast, Leithwood et al. (2019) emphasize that the principal's role has evolved from mere administration to proactive leadership that addresses emerging educational challenges such as digital transformation and inclusive education. In addition, Fullan (2020) underscores the importance of adaptability in a principal's administrative function. He argues that modern principals must navigate complex educational landscapes, including policy changes, technological advancements, and social issues affecting student learning. The principal, therefore, acts as a mediator between government regulations and the practical needs of the school community.

Principals' administrative functions can be broadly categorized into instructional leadership, human resource management, financial management, student discipline, and stakeholder engagement (Lunenburg & Ornstein, 2021). Instructional leadership entails setting academic standards, supervising curriculum implementation, and fostering professional learning communities among teachers. Human resource management involves recruiting, mentoring, and appraising staff performance. Financial management includes budgeting, fund allocation, and ensuring accountability in resource utilization. Student discipline focuses on establishing behavioral policies and conflict resolution strategies, while stakeholder engagement ensures collaboration with parents, the community, and educational authorities.

2.1.2 Achievements

Achievement has to do with a great or heroic deed or feat, and can also be looked at as an accomplishment. The achievement of principals relies on his or her administrative capacity and ability to make reasonable decision for effective administration (Onyeike & Nwosu, 2018). The way principals play their roles determine equally the academic achievement of students. Hence, Olaleye (2013) observes that whoever to be blamed, the fact remains that, the school and its organizational management has correlation with the academic achievement of the students.

It does not end in only the students but equally has a relationship with the success or achievement of the school in general. For this, Louis, Leithwood, Wahlstrom and Anderson (2010), say that principals represent nearly 25% of the variation in a school's achievement. Therefore, effective principals raise the achievement of a typical student in the school by two to seven months of learning in a single school year. On the other hand, ineffective principals lower achievement by the same amount, (Krasnoff, 2015). This work strives to find out the achievements of male and female principals through their various administrative styles.

2.2 Theoretical Framework of the Study

This study is anchored on the Administrative Management Theory

2.2.1 Administrative Management Theory

This theory was propounded by Henri Fayol (1916) and he defined it as the functional element of administrative task which is as follows:

To plan - means to study the future and arrange the plan of operations.

To command – to ensure that the staff do their work

To coordinate – means to unite and correlate all activities

To control – means to see that everything is done in accordance to the rules and instructions laid down.

Fayol (1916) equally gave out fourteen principles of managements through which he prescribed certain strategies for structuring behaviours in organizational life in order to achieve efficiency and effectiveness. These principles include:

Division of Work: Division of work on specialization increases productivity. The more skilled the labourer and management the higher productivity, because one can work at activities in which he is most capable.

Authority and Responsibility: Authority connotes the right to give orders and it therefore required to control the behaviours of organizational participants.

Discipline: There must be respect for and obedience to the rules and objectives of the organization

Unity of Command: To minimize confusion and conflicts each subordinate should receive orders and be responsible to one super-ordinate

Unity of Direction: This implies unity of purpose. An organization is more effective when everyone works towards the same objectives.

Subordination of Individual Interest: The interest of one employee or group should not prevail over the interest of the organization. Corollary, the interest of the whole supersedes the interest of the parts.

Remuneration: Pay according to performance. Pay should be fair and not exploitation.

Centralization: There should be a balance between concentration and distribution of authority in the organization. Hence, there should be delegation of authority.

Scalar Chain: There is a scalar chain of hierarchy lurking various levels and all members according to the unity of command.

Order: There should be systematic arrangement of functions for everyone in the organization.

Equity: Fairness, cordiality, kindness, and justice, based on predetermined norms.

Stability of Tenure of Personnel: Time is required for an employee to get used to new work and succeed in doing it well. Job security should be used to reward good performance.

Initiative: Subordinate should be encouraged to initiate mistake result.

Esprit de Corps (Team Spirit): “Unity is Strength” Superior performance come from a feeling of oneness, belongingness, pride and loyalty.

Nonetheless, the Henri Fayol's administrative management has recorded some strengths that made it possible for some scholars to build on it as a foundation. It facilitates organizational structure for even small business in which top-down model is exercised (senior level to the rank-and-file). It also promotes the team concept in which no individual interest is upheld as paramount but subordinated to the general interest of the company, business or school. It equally motivates employees through fair compensation in terms of salaries and wages in order for them to perform above standard. Given these and other strengths of the theory, some other authors have built on Fayol's work. For instances, Urwick and Gulick (1937) worked upon Fayol's elements of administration and provided more articulate and up-to-date principle of management with the acronym POSDCORB which depicts seven administrative procedures: – planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating, reporting and budgeting. These functions overlap and the performance of one cannot be neatly separated from the other, thereby, making management a composite process.

Moreover, this was further worked upon by Enaohwo and Eferakeya in 1989 by introducing or adding 'Evaluation' as a way of making a complete function of manager. Hence, the acronym now becomes POSDCORBE where the last letter E represents evaluation. It is so because, the reporting function does not entail evaluation but an aspect of evaluation. However, despite the strengths of Fayol's theory of Management, there are some limitations or weaknesses to it. It is management-oriented theory in the sense that it does not give much attention to the problems of workers; it shows a lack of importance to informal organization or groups; its concepts are borrowed from military science; such as 'commanding' and not dictating. Simon (1976) sees the theory as suffering from superficiality, oversimplification and lack of realism. Seeing that unity of command is not compatible with division of labour, he says that the theory is inconsistent.

This theory is linked to this study in the sense that the roles of principals are contained in these principles beginning from planning to evaluation and it will make the principals to involve others (esprit de corps) in pursuit of the common goal bearing in mind that maintenance of discipline as well as unity of direction in working together, will lead to achievement of the objectives. The theory is linked to this present study on the ground that the application of the Administrative Management Theory to this study helps the principals, while administering secondary schools, to see the need for common goal otherwise, any lack or indiscipline act in one area will certainly affect the entire system.

2.3 Empirical Review

Pour Rajab, Mahdinezhad, Bijandi, Basri, and Nazari (2011) carried out a research on the Educational Administrators' Performance and Organizational Health: Key Factors for Sustainable Development in High Schools. It was part of a correlation research which was been carried out to study the relationship between the performance of the educational administrators and the organizational health to obtain Sustainable Development in Iranian high schools in Tehran, Iran. The educational objectives of the research were: ability to induce the proper organizational climate for the employees in carrying, their tasks and responsibilities, utilizing the available material and human resources as required, creating the needed integration and synchronicity between the elements and components of the organization and finally arousing his/her colleagues and subordinates to work and being active effectively.

The sampling method was cluster sampling and there was a sample size of 180 teachers. The research instrumentation consists of two questionnaires: the school organizational health and the administrator performance. The research data were analysed in the quantitative level by using inferential and descriptive statistics, and for describing the variables the Pearson correlation coefficient and coefficient of determination

were used. Findings show that there is positive and significant relationship between organizational health and the performance of the principals. The results of the study also indicate that there is a relationship between organizational health with the principal performance in the areas of education and teaching programmes, student and staff affairs. The educational implication, therefore, is that when principals perform their roles properly, there will be positive and healthy growth of the school. This present study is related to the reviewed study from the view point that it is set out to consider principals' performance in playing their roles in administering secondary schools but differs from it by looking at discipline and not only development as the research targeted. It will close the gap of getting disciplined products for the higher level of education and society at large apart from school development.

In considering the administrative achievement of both male and female principals in secondary schools, researchers have come up with several literatures. On her own, Oboegbulem (2013) conducted a research on Administrative Competencies of Female Principals in Secondary Schools in Nsukka Education Zone. The study investigated the administrative competencies of female principals in secondary schools in Nsukka Education zone of Enugu State, Nigeria.

Three research questions and one null hypothesis guided the study. A 15-item questionnaire was constructed to collect the necessary data for the study. Purposive sampling technique was adopted in selecting all the 10 secondary schools headed by female principals. Stratified random sampling technique was used in selecting 20% of the 818 male and 517 female teachers in Nsukka Education zone. This gave a total of 164 males and 103 females. Means and t-test were employed in data analysis. A mean of 2.50 was taken as the agreement level of the items.

The result of the study showed that female principals possess administrative skills and competencies for effective secondary school management. It has an educational implication that female be not left out in appointing personnel to the office of principals. This present work closes the gap created by comparing male and female principals' capacities.

Karadağ and Bektaş (2014) conducted a research on Women Administrators in Education: Leadership behaviours Assessment According to Teachers' Perceptions. The research was carried out in Eskişehir Osmangazi University, Turkey. The purpose of this study was to reveal leadership behaviours of women administrators in education. The research was designed using the survey model and it was conducted with 936 randomly selected teachers who work on the schools administered by women administrators, in Istanbul. The Leader Behaviours Description Questionnaire was used for data collection. T-test and ANOVA techniques was used for data analysis. As the result of the research, it has been found that women administrators usually show "initiation of structure" type leadership behaviours compared to "Consideration" type leadership behaviours. The educational implication is that gender bias should not come into play in selecting principals. This study tends to show also that female principals can achieve much and sometimes, even more than their male counterparts by way of finding out their administrative styles.

Matheri, Cheloti and Malwa (2015) carried out a research on Principals' Gender and Management Effectiveness in Secondary Schools: Case of Mtito Andei Division, Kenya. The purpose of the study was to determine the effects of principals' gender on management effectiveness in secondary schools in Mtito-Andei Division, Kenya. The study sought to establish the relationship between the Principals' gender and their effectiveness in management of the discipline, staff, students and school finance. The study used ex-post facto research design. Simple random sampling was used to select the respondents for the study. The sample size was 28 principals and

140 teachers. Data was collected by use of questionnaires and interview schedules and was analysed by use of descriptive and inferential statistics. Conceptually, the chi-square test of independence statistic was computed. In hypotheses the four scores in management of discipline, management of staff personnel, management of students and management of financial resources were converted from continuous data to discreet data (categories) respectively and then Chi-square used to test the hypotheses. The researcher adopted a significance level of 0.05. The results of the data analysis show that there was a significant relationship between the principals' gender and effectiveness in management of discipline. It was also found out that there was no significant relationship between the principles gender and their effectiveness in personnel management, student management and financial management. The implication on educational sector is such that gender consideration should not be left out. This study is related to the above work in considering gender difference in administration but done in a different environment. It also covers the gap created by the research by considering the gender that achieves more; that is, female principals achieving more than their male counterparts.

Okoroma (2016) conducted a research on the Administrative Abilities of Male and Female Principals and Goals Achievement in Nigerian Public Secondary Schools. The research was carried out in Rivers state, in Nigeria. The objectives of the study bordered on the management capabilities of male administrators who have held sway in Nigeria's school system and whether the secondary school system can be better managed by female administrators than the domineering male gender? 245 vice-principals of secondary schools in Rivers State, were sampled. Out of the 245 principals only 63 were females and 182 males. For a balance, the sample of the study consisted of 63 vice principals from the schools administered by male principals and 63 vice-principals from the schools administered by female principals. Out of the 2,394 teachers in the selected schools 1197 or 50% were chosen for the study and this gave a total of 1,323 respondents. An instrument known as 'Principals' Administrative Abilities Assessment Questionnaire (PAAAQ) was used for data gathering. The chi-square statistical method was used for the analysis of data. The finding of the study revealed that female principals are better achievers of school goals than their male counterparts. The educational implication is that more female be appointed to the office of secondary school principals. The present research is related to it as it is set out to look at the gender difference in principals' roles in administration of secondary schools but differs from it by being conducted in a different state and education zone.

In a way of finding out what the constraints are in administration of urban and rural secondary schools, Morrison and Afokeghene (2020) carried out a research on Constraints to Principals Administration Effectiveness in Secondary Schools in Delta. The study investigated the Constraints to principals' administration effectiveness in secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. To guide the study, four research questions were raised and four hypotheses formulated for the study at a significance level of 0.05. The design of the study was the descriptive survey which permits the description of conditions as they exist in their natural setting. The population of the study comprised all the 448 secondary school principals in delta state. The sample size for the study was one hundred and twenty (120) principals using the random sampling techniques. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire developed by the researcher. Data analysis was done using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and z-test to test the null hypotheses at an alpha level of 0.05.

The result of the study among others showed that: there is no significant difference between the mean perception of urban and rural principals on staff personnel administrative constraints to principals administrative effectiveness in secondary schools, there is a significant difference between the mean perception of urban and rural principals on facilities and equipment constraints to principals administrative effectiveness in secondary

school, there is no significant difference between the mean perception of urban and rural principals on funding constraints to principals' administrative effectiveness. It equally indicated that there is no significant difference between the mean perception of urban and rural principals on funding constraints to principals administrative effectiveness. The research above differs from this present study from the point of view that it was carried out in another Education Zone and for the fact that it considered only the constraints to the administrative roles of principals.

Oboegbulem (2013) conducted a research on Constraints to Administrative Leadership Role of Secondary School Principals in Owerri Education Zone of Imo State, Nigeria. The objective of this study was to investigate through survey, the constraints to administrative roles of principals in Owerri Education Zone. A 25-item questionnaire gained information on financial, physical and equipment constraints and staff personnel administration constraints to administrative leadership roles of the principals. A mean of 2.50 indicated the acceptance of an item as a constraint. 50% of the total number of principals in the zone was sampled using proportionate purposive sampling technique. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the internal reliability of the instrument. The findings of the study showed among others; inadequate funds to procure facilities and equipment, inadequate funds for organizing seminars and workshops, poor condition of service for teachers, insufficient vehicles for supervisory, duties and other administrative duties, poor teacher development plan and no criteria for positing newly recruited teachers, as constraints to the administrative leadership roles of the principals. The work above is related to this study in its consideration of factors hindering the role of principals but differs from this present study from the areas of different Education Zone and not diversifying the Urban-Rural situations.

Preston, Jakubiec and Kooymaus (2013) conducted a research on Common Challenges faced by Principals: A Review of the Literature. The research was carried out at the University of Prince Edward, Island. The purpose of the research was the thematic presentation of common challenges associated with the role of the rural principal. The research design used for this study was document analysis, which involves collection and analysis of available data published on a specific topic, research question, or social phenomenon for the purpose of finding and or understanding patterns and thematic regularities. In this literature review, the researchers delimited their search to work published from 2003–2013. A limitation of this study is that it represents data predominantly from American, Canadian, and Australian rural settings, restricting a global applicability of results. The findings of the study highlighted that many rural principal candidates face a hiring disadvantage if they do not have a historical connection with the community advertising a position. Additional challenges include juggling diverse responsibilities, lack of professional development and resources, gender discrimination, and issues surrounding school accountability and change. This work is related to the present study in its search for principals' constraints in administration but differs from it as it was carried out in another education zone.

Onderi and Makori (2013) carried out a research on Secondary School Principals in Nyamira County, Kenya: Issues and Challenges. The purpose of this study was to establish the challenges that confront principals of secondary schools in Nyamira County in Kenya. The study adopted a descriptive survey and questionnaires were employed to collect data. The study sample consisted of 87 principals purposively selected from schools in the County. The quantitative data from questionnaires was analysed with the aid of SPSS (statistical package for social science). The study established that principals faced serious challenges which included interference from sponsors, inadequate funds, inadequate resources and lack of qualified teachers among others. The study also identified the following as serious issues: teenage pregnancy, bullying, alcohol and drugs, violence and truancy among others. Such challenges and issues negatively impacted on the schools' entire life including examination

performances. The educational implication is that the stakeholders in education should mobilize and empower principals for the smooth running of schools. The above research is related to the present study by its consideration of constraints to principals' effectiveness in their administrative roles but differed from it by being conducted in another education zone.

3.0 Methodology

The research design for this study was descriptive survey research design. It was targeted at providing the opinions of the respondents on what the role of principals are in the administration of secondary schools of Nsukka education zone. The study was carried out in Nsukka education zone of Enugu state, Nigeria. This education zone comprises of three local government areas, namely; Igbo Etiti, Nsukka and Uzo-Uwani local government areas. This Education Zone is the surrounding place of the northern part of Enugu State (southern part of Nigeria), the home site of the famous University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN) and shares boundary with Kogi and Anambra States. The zone has the minority at the urban area and majority at the rural area, all comprising of Igbo speaking People (with the exception of visitors). The area is an agricultural-trade centre for yams, cassava, corn, pigeon peas, palm oil and kernels. They practice weaving as their traditional local craft, and have much respect for the culture of traditional marriage and burial. It is an area with greater number of Christian worshippers and few African traditional worshippers who worship Odo, Akatakpa, Omabe, and Ekewo. Politically, it is the location of the Enugu North Senatorial Zone with about the population of 309,633 (2006 census). It comprises of mostly farmers and few middle-class civil servants with basic income. They are mostly poor indigenes but with very much interest in education given the influence of University of Nigeria Nsukka. The choice of this area was based on the fact that it was the place the researcher observed the rate of indiscipline and neglect of roles-playing on the side of principals.

The population of the study comprises of all the 61 principals of the 61 public secondary schools in Nsukka Education zone {Source: Post Primary School Management Board (PPSMB) Nsukka planning research and statistical unit (2018/2019)}. The sample size of the study is 53. This sample was determined using the formula: $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$, where n = sample size, N = Population, 1 = constant and e = Error term or Significant level (0.05) as was recommended by Taro Yamane (1967). This sample comprises 53 of the total population of 61 principals selected from the secondary schools using simple random sampling technique. The instruments for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher. The questionnaire was administered to the respondents, which included 53 principals, directly. The responses for each item of the research question were tallied and weighted using 4-point rating scale. The total weighted frequencies were used to determine the mean score for each item. Mean score from 2.50 was considered acceptable while any mean score below 2.50 was considered rejected. The mean and the standard deviation were used to analyse the five research questions posed for the study. The t-test statistics was used to test two Null hypotheses formulated for the study at 0.05 level of significance.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT PRESENTATION

4.1 Data Analysis

Research Question One: Using the appropriate management styles, what are the administrative achievements of male and female principals in their administrative roles?

Table 4 - Cluster D: Mean and Standard Deviation of Administrative Achievements of Male and Female Principals in their Administrative Roles

S/N	Items	N = 53	\bar{X}	SD	Dec
1	Male principals achieve more on school plants than their female counterparts.		2.96	0.71	A
2	Male principals achieve more on discipline and school climate		3.00	0.69	A
3	Female principals do more on students' instruction and academic performance.		2.79	0.58	A
4	Female principals do more on Principal-Teacher-Student relationship.		2.72	0.56	A
5	Male and female principals make achievements on areas of structure and facilities for the school.		3.11	0.73	A
Grand Mean			2.92	0.65	A

Key: N = Number of Subjects, \bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Dec = Decision, A = Accepted & R = Rejected

The grand mean response score of 2.92 with its associated standard deviation 0.65 which is above the mean rating bench mark of 2.50 indicated that respondents agreed with the five items under cluster D as the administrative achievements of male and female principals in their administrative roles in secondary schools

Research Question Two

What are the administrative constraints of principals of urban and rural secondary schools?

Table 2 - Cluster E: Mean and Standard Deviation of Administrative Constraints of Principals of Urban and Rural Secondary Schools

S/N	Items	N = 53	\bar{X}	SD	Dec
6	Principals of schools in urban and rural areas face financial constraint.		3.25	0.83	A
7	Principals of schools in urban areas are challenged by students' indiscipline.		3.04	0.72	A
8	Principals of schools in rural areas face mobility problem		2.79	0.58	A
9	Principals of schools in rural areas lack manpower (qualified and enough teachers).		3.19	0.77	A
10	Principals of schools in urban and rural areas experience structural constraints.		3.18	0.75	A
Grand Mean			3.09	0.73	A

Key: N = Number of Subjects, \bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Dec = Decision, A = Accepted & R = Rejected

The grand mean response score of 3.09 with its associated standard deviation 0.73 which is above the mean rating bench mark of 2.50 indicated that respondents agreed with the five items under cluster E as the administrative constraints of principals of urban and rural secondary schools.

4.2 Hypotheses Testing

H₀1: There is no significant difference in the mean score rating of male and female principals on the extent principals establish discipline among students and staff.

Table 3: t-test Analysis on the extent male and female principals establish discipline among students and staff

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	T	Df	Std error diff.	Sig.	Dec.
Male	42	36.93	5.191	1.809	51	0.713	0.000	S
Female	11	33.82	4.579					

The data in table six tested hypothesis one and the result showed that the t-test value for the difference in the mean score rating of male and female principal on the extent principals establish discipline among students and staff is 1.809 with an associated probability score of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 alpha levels. This indicated significant since 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance set for the study. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean score rating of male and female principals on the extent principals establish discipline among students and staff.

H₀2: There is no significant difference in the mean score rating of principals on administrative constraint of principals in urban and rural secondary schools.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of Principal's Administrative Constraints in Urban and Rural Secondary Schools

Location	N	\bar{X}	SD	t	Df	Std error diff.	Sig.	Dec.
Urban	15	36.00	4.614	-2.47	51	1.596	0.806	NS
Rural	38	36.39	5.450					

The data in table seven tested hypothesis two and the result showed that the t-test value for the difference in the mean score rating of principals on administrative constraint of principals in urban and rural secondary schools is -2.47 with an associated probability score of 0.806 which is greater than 0.05 alpha levels. This indicated no significant since 0.806 is greater than 0.05 level of significance set for the study. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference in the mean score rating of principals on administrative constraint of principals in urban and rural secondary schools.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The results of the analysis presented showed the following findings:

1. There is gender difference in established discipline between male and female principals in favour of male principals.
2. School location (urban and rural) has no significant influence on administrative constraints of principals in Nsukka Education zone.

5.2 Conclusion

Based on the findings and hypotheses testing, these conclusions emanated from the study:

Both male and female principals have managerial competence in administration of secondary schools in Nsukka Education zone. However, male principals do better in the area of discipline than their female counterparts. Principals of both urban and rural secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone are constrained with finance, structure/facilities and indiscipline, thereby hindering their effective managerial abilities.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher recommends the following;

- i. The Community or the Government should build quarters to house principals and teachers coming from outside the community in which the school is located.
- ii. The School Management Board should regularize their inspection and supervision to schools to ensure functionality of principals and staff.

References

- All Nigeria Conference of Principals of Secondary Schools (ANCORPSS). (2016). Principals year book. Nsukka: Mike Social Publishers.
- Alokan, F. B., & Arijesuyo, A. E. (2013). Rural and urban differential in students' academic performance among secondary school students in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Social Research*, 3(3), 19–33.
- Bush, T. (2021). *Leadership and management in education: International perspectives*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2014). *National policy on education (6th ed.)*. Lagos: NERDC.
- Fullan, M. (2020). *The new meaning of educational change (5th ed.)*. Teachers College Press.
- Hallinger, P., & Murphy, J. (2020). Assessing the instructional management behavior of principals. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 56(3), 432–460.
- Hoy, W. K., & Miskel, C. G. (2018). *Educational administration: Theory, research, and practice (10th ed.)*. McGraw-Hill.
- Krasnoff, B. (2015). Leadership qualities of effective principals: Northwest comprehensive. Retrieved from <https://www.semanticscholar.org> (Accessed February 2, 2020).
- Leithwood, K., Sun, J., & Pollock, K. (2019). *How school leaders contribute to student success: The four paths framework*. Springer.
- Louis, K. S., Leithwood, K., Wahlstrom, K. L., & Anderson, S. E. (2010). *Investigating the link to improved student learning: Final report of research findings*. Retrieved from <http://www.wallacefoundation.org/knowledge-center/school-leadership/investigating-the-links-to-improved-student-learning.aspx>
- Lunenburg, F. C., & Ornstein, A. C. (2012). *Educational administration: Concepts and practices*. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth Cengage Learning.
- Lunenburg, F. C., & Ornstein, A. C. (2021). *Educational administration: Concepts and practices (7th ed.)*. Cengage Learning.

- Matheri, E. W., Cheloti, S. K., & Malwa, D. M. (2015). Principals' gender and management effectiveness in secondary schools: Case of Mtito Andei Division, Kenya. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(14), 12–17.
- Morrison, I. O., & Afokeghene, O. S. (2018). Constraints to principals' administration effectiveness in secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Studies*, 8(3), 10–19.
- Murphy, J., & Torre, D. (2014). *Creating productive cultures in schools: For students, teachers and parents*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin.
- Oboegbulem, A. I. (2013). Administrative competencies of female principals in secondary schools in Nsukka Education Zone. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(11), 11–17.
- Okoroma, N. S., & Walson, O. B. A. (2010). Factors that militate the effective implementation of the UBE programme in Nigeria. *Journal of Education Research and Policies*, 3(4), 21–32.
- Okoroma, N. S. (2016). Administrative abilities of male and female principals and goals achievement in Nigerian public secondary schools. *Journal of Culture, Society and Development*, 20(6), 1–36.
- Onderi, H., & Makori, A. (2013). Secondary school principals in Nyamira County in Kenya: Issues and challenges. Retrieved from [http://www.erint.savap.org.pk/PDF/vol.1\(1\)/ERInt.2013\(1.1-04\).pdf](http://www.erint.savap.org.pk/PDF/vol.1(1)/ERInt.2013(1.1-04).pdf)
- Onyeike, V. C., & Nwosu, C. M. (2018). Principals' administrative and supervisory roles for teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Rivers State. *British Journal of Education*, 6(6), 38–49.
- Orodho, A. G. (2014). Coalescing nutrition and health programmes to enhance pupils' participation in basic education as a panacea to socio-economic development of marginalized communities in Kenya in the 21st century. Paper presented at the African Nutrition Conference, North Coast Beach Hotel, Mombasa, Kenya.
- Osakwe, R. N. (2012). Supervisory functions of secondary school principals and factors competing with these functions. *Journal of Research and Method in Education*, 1(3), 13–19.
- Pourrajab, M., Mahdinezhad, M., Bijandi, S., Basri, R., & Nazari, K. (2011). Educational administrators' performance and organizational health: Key factors for sustainable development in high schools. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, 2(5), 397–401.
- Preston, J. P., Jakubiec, B. A. E., & Kooymans, R. (2013). Common challenges faced by rural principals: A review of the literature. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1022612.pdf>
- Simon, H. A. (1976). *Administrative behavior* (3rd ed.). New York, NY: Free Press.

Udor, U. O. E. (2015). Effective administration of secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria: A panacea for academic excellence. *Science Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*, 2015(214), 1–3.

Ugwu, L. C. (2009). Delegatory function of secondary school principals in Nsukka Education Zone of Enugu State (Unpublished master's dissertation). Education Foundations Department, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.